

SOCIAL SCIENCES

UDC 316.28

THEORY OF MASS COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Currently, Kazakhstan is intensively introducing new information and communication technologies (ICTs), increasing competition from foreign media, and gradually switching to new standards for TV and radio companies, telecom operators, and digital broadcasting in the country.

Keywords: *New media, Mass media.*

Information processes are global in nature, but have national characteristics of the emerging state. With the acquisition of sovereignty in Kazakhstan, a new system of mass media was formed. De-monopolization of the telecommunications and broadcasting sectors has been implemented. The emergence of new media organizations, private and joint-stock media, and TV and radio companies has made it possible to quickly and easily enter the media market, constantly feeling the need for information resources and messaging.

Currently, the mobile telephony market is actively developing in the country. The Ministry of Transport and Communications of the Republic of Kazakhstan is actively working to introduce the 3G cellular communication standard in the territory of the Republic. By the beginning of 2012, there were 24 million mobile subscribers in the country (the population of Kazakhstan as of May 4, 2012 was 16.73 million people).

Internet users are growing rapidly in Kazakhstan. So, from 2000 to 2009, the number of Internet users in Kazakhstan increased from 70 thousand to 2.3 million people (increased 30 times). By 2010, the number of Internet users was 3.5 million. At the beginning of 2012, there were 8.7 million Internet users in the country.

Currently, new media, in particular social networks, are rapidly developing all over the world, and Kazakhstan is no exception. Facebook is one of the most frequently used social networks in the world and the most frequently used query in the Google search engine. As noted by the Executive Director of the company "Intenews-Kazakhstan" M. Yelshibayeva, "if Russian Internet users like such social networks as Odnoklassniki and Vkontakte, Kazakhstanians prefer Facebook and My World. In addition, Kazakh is one of the four most frequently used languages on Facebook. (1).

The first cable TV networks in the country began to be created in the late 1980s. Currently, 146 cable TV operators provide cable TV services in the republic, mainly in regional centers and major cities of the country. The country is rapidly developing a cable television system, where subscribers of this type of broadcasting are offered more than 100 channels. In March 2003, the Association of Cable TV Operators was established in

Kazakhstan. The main cable TV players in Kazakhstan are:

- Alma-TV JSC,
- Alem Communications Holding, which includes Digital TV networks (Almaty), G-Media (Pavlodar), Sekatel (Aktau, Astana, Almaty) and 5 other companies in the cities of Taraz, Aktau, Zhanaozen, Uralsk, Ak-tobe.
- tv icon,
- Kazakhtelecom and iDTV.

According to experts, the pay TV market in Kazakhstan is growing by 15-20 percent annually.

Kazakhstan is actively implementing new information technologies in the mass media. A large territory of the country contributes to the development of satellite television-television without borders. Kazakhstan's Baikonur cosmodrome, a space rocket launch center, provides great assistance in this direction. Thanks to the Zharyk satellite TV system, it became possible to broadcast TV programs from the Northern and southern capitals to all regions of Kazakhstan, as well as TV programs from some countries of Russia, Uzbekistan, China, and Mongolia. peripheral broadcasting.

In July 2011, the second Kazakh satellite "Kazsat-2" was launched, providing the republic with satellite communications, as well as digital television and radio broadcasting. This satellite is intended for domestic broadcasting and telecommunications. And with the launch of Kazsat-3 in 2013, the republic will not depend on foreign telecom operators. For the creation of the third satellite in 2011-2013, Kazakhstan will allocate 24 billion tenge (2) (1 ruble = 4.6 tenge, 1 dollar = 149 tenge).

Currently, the state program "Electronic Government" is being implemented, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated November 10, 2004. Its goal is to create a corporate information system throughout the country. It consists of two stages: the first one is informative and the second one is interactive. An e-government web portal has been launched as a single window, bringing together all the Internet resources of government agencies.

Kazakhstan has started developing 6 national websites. The first is the national educational website,

which hosts electronic textbooks for schoolchildren and students. The second is the first national medical web portal for a wide range of users. There will be a project of the electronic library of Kazakhstan. A large portal "National heritage of Kazakhstan" is planned, containing information about the history, culture, ethnic group of Kazakhstan, its peoples. There will be two more portals: a portal for legal entities and a business portal that reveals the country's business potential.

The most important priority for Kazakhstan is the country's transition to digital broadcasting by 2015, which is due to global trends – the transition period of the International Telecommunication Union "Geneva-2006 "(2007-2015).) introduction of digital television broadcasting in coordination with broadcasting. Kazakhstan has developed a state program for the development of digital television and radio broadcasting in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2008-2015. Its implementation requires the allocation of funds from the national budget, as well as extra-budgetary sources: direct domestic and foreign investments totaling 36.165 million tenge (3).

On July 3, 2012, Kazakhstan launched a digital terrestrial TV broadcasting network in the cities of Astana, Almaty, Karaganda, Zhezkazgan and Zhanaozen. In total, the network includes 827 radio and television stations. DVB-T2 broadcast standard with CUD. Two multiplexes equivalent to 30 SDTV channels are broadcast in Astana, Almaty and regional centers, and one multiplex of 15 TV channels is broadcast in other localities. The construction of the digital terrestrial television network is scheduled to be completed in 2015. The national TV and radio broadcasting operator Kaztelradio JSC provides parallel operation of the existing analog broadcasting network.

To increase the competitiveness of domestic television production, it is planned to create a global multi-segment broadcasting network, which provides for the appearance of the largest news agency in Central Asia. The Ministry of Communications and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan (now the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan) opened a new TV and Radio Complex in Astana in December 2011. Currently, the draft law "On TV and Radio Broadcasting" has been approved, which regulates issues related to digital broadcasting, as well as other issues of great importance for the development of the industry.

If in 1990 there were only two national TV channels in the republic, then 4 radio programs and about 400 magazines and newspapers were published. Currently, more than 7 thousand people are registered. Mass media, of which 3,018 mass media operate on a permanent basis. The share of print media (newspapers and magazines) is 91% of the total number of mass media, electronic media - 8.5%: 63 TV channels and 42 radio companies, 146 cable TV operators and 6 satellite broadcasters, 0.5% - news agencies.

The share of non-State media in the country's information market is 85 percent. The largest contribution among print media:

- social and political publications-36%,
- information -32%,

- scientific and analytical -27%.

Almost half of the total number of newspapers is published in Kazakh and Russian, there are newspapers published only in Kazakh or only in Russian, some newspapers are Uyghur, Korean, English, German, etc. Foreign news agencies are accredited in Kazakhstan: ITAR-TASS, RIA Novosti, Reuters, Franz-Press, Xinhua, etc.

Since 2005, funding for supporting ethnic media and demonstrating interethnic relations has been increased more than 4 times. In Kazakhstan, newspapers and magazines are published in 15 languages, radio programs-in eight, TV programs-in 11 languages, the state allocates funds to support the activities of 19 ethnic media outlets, a total of 33 (4).

Electronic media coverage in the country is provided by 11 TV channels and 5 radio stations. Programs at the national level: Khabar TV channels – 98.19%, Kazakhstan-98.06%, El-Arna – 83.58%, First Channel Eurasia-78.82%, Kazakh Radio-93.2%. There is a satellite channel "Caspionet", which broadcasts in Central Asia, the Middle East, Europe and North Africa. In 2011, Caspionet began broadcasting in the United States, and its programs also became available in America (5). Rural localities are mainly covered by the state-owned Khabar, Kazakhstan, and El-Arna channels.

Non-governmental republican TV and radio companies broadcasting at their own expense on a large territory of the republic: KVN, NTK, Channel 31, STV, Radio Russia Asia, Europe plus Kazakhstan, Radio NS.

About 2,400 foreign media outlets, including 2309 newspapers and magazines, 83 TV and radio programs, are distributed on the domestic Kazakh information market. More than 80 foreign media outlets are accredited in Kazakhstan. About 90% of the total number of foreign media titles distributed on the territory of the republic in Russian, 5% - in English, 5% - in other languages of the world.

The largest foreign media distribution networks in the republic: Kazpost JSC, AiF-Kazakhstan Joint Venture LLP, Eurasia-Press JSC, Alma-TV JSC, Sekatel LLP, Kazcenter-TV, Katelko+. The total volume of mass media distributed by these structures is 70 percent of the total volume.

Kazakhstan was the first among the Central Asian states in the CIS to start broadcasting using advanced technologies using digital television, a multimedia satellite system for transmitting a television signal and live television broadcasting.

Today, the leading role in the country is played by computerized information communication networks, which are introduced into our lives in different directions, within individual states, regions, and at the transnational level, forming a wide network of connections, whose services are often compared. functions of the nervous system.

The information technology revolution has strengthened the introduction and development of global QMS, satellite, cable TV, mobile telephony are rapidly spreading in the republic, the number of web publications, information multimedia resources is growing, fiber-optic communication and paid video are developed. Socio-economic changes in Kazakhstan's

society have determined the direction of development of new information technologies and mass media in the country.

The trend of preparing national broadcast programs that can compete with international programs is becoming more and more noticeable, the launch of its own communication satellite provides direct television broadcasting throughout the country, specialized cable television services are being created, digital and interactive broadcasting is gradually being introduced, and the Internet is actively developing.

The politically strong trend towards deregulation, the country's openness to expanding the perception of global messages, and the commercialization of television systems contribute to accelerating integration processes, which, in turn, increases the competitiveness of new participants in the information market.

The creation of a market for information services, the emergence of various operators, networks of communication firms, and new TV and radio channels in

Kazakhstan are factors that influence the prospects for the development of modern media in the country. Modernization of a number of countries and regions can be successful if the society retains its uniqueness in the context of communication and economic globalization with the active development of new information technologies and the latest mass media.

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